

A new negative feedback mechanism for MAPK pathway inactivation through Srk1 MAPKAP kinase.

Maribel Marquina^{ad*}, Eva Lambea^{al*}, Mercé Carmona^c, Marta Sánchez-Marinas^{a2}, Sandra López-Aviles^b, José Ayte^c, Elena Hidalgo^c and Rosa Aligue^{a+}

Supplementary Information

Supplementary Fig. S1

Wis1

```
MSSPNNQPLS CSLRQLSISP TAPPGDVGTP GSLLSLSSSS
SSNTDSSGSS LGSLSLNSNS SGSDNDSKVS SPSREIPSDP
PLPRAVPTVR LGRSTSSRSR NSLNLDMKDP SEKPRRSLPT
AAGQNNIGSP PTPPGPFPGG LSTDIQEKLK AFHASRSKSM
PEVVNKISSP TTPIVGMGQR GSYPLPNSQL AGRLSNSPVK
SPNMPESGLA KSLAAARNPL LNRPTSFNRQ TRIRRAPP GK
LDLSNSNPTS PVSPSSMASR RGLNIPPTLK QAVSETPFST
FSDILDAKSG TLNFKNKAVL NSEGVNFSSG SSFRINMSEI
IKLEELGKGN YGVVYKALHQ PTGVTMALKE IRLSLEEATF
NQIIMELDIL HKAVSPYIVD FYGAFFVEGS VFICMEYMDA
GSMDKLYAGG IKDEGVLART AYAVVQGLKT LKEEHNIHR
DVKPTNVLVN SNGQVKLCDF GVSGNLVASI SKTNIGCQSY
MAPERIRVGG PTNGVLTYTV QADVWSLGLT ILEMALGAYP
YPPESTYTSIF AQLSAICDGD PPSLPDSFSP EARDFVNKCL
NKNPSLRPDY HELANHPWLL KYQNADVDMASWAKGALKEK
GEKRS
```

Fig. S1. Wis1 protein sequence.

Srk1 consensus phosphorylation sites in Wis1 (shown in blue).

New Srk1 non consensus phosphorylation site in Wis1 (shown in red).

Wis1 accession number X62631.1 and SPBC409.07c.

Supplementary Table S1

Strain	Genotype	Origin
RA2502	<i>h- styl::ura4+ leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Lab stock
RA0770	<i>h- wis1::ura4+ leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Lab stock
RA1102	<i>h- srk1::kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Lab stock
RA0772	<i>h- atf1::ura4+ leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Lab stock
RA1449	<i>h- srk1::kanMX6 atf1::ura4+ leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Lab stock
RA1380	<i>h- srk1:HA:kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Lab stock
RA3917	<i>h- srk1-K153A:kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Lab stock
RA1843	<i>h- pyp1:12myc:ura4+ leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Dr. P. Russell
RA1920	<i>h- pyp1:12myc:ura4+ srk1::kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	This study
RA1844	<i>h- pyp2:12myc:ura4+ leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Dr. P. Russell
RA1922	<i>h- pyp2:12myc:ura4+ srk1::kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	This study
RA1423	<i>h+ pyp1::leu2 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Dr. J. Millar
RA1424	<i>h+ pyp2::leu2 leu1-32 ura4-D18 ade6-704</i>	Dr. J. Millar
RA1866	<i>h- pyp1::ura4+ srk1::kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	This study
RA1919	<i>h- pyp2::ura4+ srk1::kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	This study
RA1973	<i>h+ wis1::kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Lab stock
RA2152	<i>h- wis1-DD:ura4+ leu1-32</i>	lab stock
RA1425	<i>h- wis1:12myc::ura4+ leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Dr. P. Russell
RA1563	<i>h- wis1:12myc::ura4+ srk1::kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	This study
RA0705	<i>h- styl:6His-HA:ura4⁺ leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Dr. J. Millar
RA3138	<i>wis1:HA:kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	Lab stock
RA4025	<i>wis1:TE/SD(ED)-HA:kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	This study
RA4024	<i>h+ wis1:5A-HA:kanMX6 leu1-32 ura4-D18</i>	This study
RA1579	<i>h- cdc25-9A:ura4+ leu1-32</i>	lab stock

Table S1. Strain used.

Supplementary Table S2

Plasmid	Sites	Origin
pGEX-KG- <i>srk1</i>	NdeI-NotI	Lab stock
pGEX-KG- <i>srk1K153A</i>	NdeI-NotI	Lab stock
pGEX-KG- <i>styl</i>	NdeI-NotI	Dra. E. Hidalgo
pGEX-KG- <i>stylKA</i>	NdeI-NotI	Dra. E. Hidalgo
pGEX-KG- <i>atf1</i>	NdeI-NotI	Dr. J. Millar
pREP41- <i>srk1-HA</i>	NdeI-NotI	Lab stock
pREP1- <i>srk1-HA</i>	NdeI-NotI	Lab stock
pREP1- <i>srk1-K153A-HA</i>	NdeI-NotI	Lab stock
pGEX-KG- <i>wisl</i>	NdeI-NotI	This study
pGEX-KG- <i>wisl-5A</i>	NdeI-NotI	This study
pGEX-KG- <i>wisl-T225E/S226D</i>	NdeI-NotI	This study
pGEX-KG- <i>wisl-K349R</i>	NdeI-NotI	This study
pGEX-KG- <i>wisl-4A-K349R</i>	NdeI-NotI	This study
pGEX-KG- <i>wisl-5A-K349R</i>	NdeI-NotI	This study

Table S2. Plasmids used

Supplementary Table S3

Oligonucleotide	Sequence	Objective
<i>Srk1 fwd</i>	5' CACACACATATGCGTTTTAAAAGT ATTCAGCAAATATCGAGGA ^{3'}	Oligos to clone <i>srk1</i> and <i>srk1T463A</i> genes in pGEX and pREP1 plasmids containing NdeI and NotI sites respectively.
<i>Srk1 rev</i>	5' CACACAGCGGCCGCCACTTTTTGT CGATGTCGACGATTATAC ^{3'}	
<i>Wis1-K349R 5'</i>	5' GGTGTCACTATGGCCTTGCGCGAA ATTAGGTTGTC ^{3'}	Oligos to mutate K349 of <i>wis1</i> gene to Arg (in red).
<i>Wis1-K349R 3'</i>	5' GGACAACCTAATTTCCGCGCAAGGC CATAGTGACACC ^{3'}	
<i>Wis1-S17A fwd</i>	5' CGCGCGCATATGTCTTCTCCAAAT AATCAACCCTTGCTTGCTCATTGAG ACAGCTGGCTATTCTCCTACCGCA CCTCCCGG ^{3'}	Oligos to mutate S17 of <i>wis1</i> gene to Ala (in red) containing NdeI and NotI sites respectively.
<i>Wis1 rev</i>	5' GGCCTCTTAAAGAGAAAGGTGAA AAAAGAAGCTGCGGCCGCCGCGCG G ^{3'}	
<i>Wis1-S96A fwd</i>	5' GCCTACGGTCAGACTTGGCAGATC TACGGCCAGTCGGAGTCGTAACCTCT CTTAACCTTGAC ^{3'}	Oligos to mutate S96 of <i>wis1</i> gene to Ala (in red).
<i>Wis1-S96A rev</i>	5' GTCAAGGTTAAGAGAGTTACGACT CCGACTGGCCGTAGATCTGCCAAGT CTGACCGTAGGC ^{3'}	
<i>Wis1-S159A fwd</i>	5' GGCCTTCCATGCATCTAGATCAA AGCAATGCCGGAAGTAGTCAACAAG ATCAG ^{3'}	Oligos to mutate S159 of <i>wis1</i> gene to Ala (in red).
<i>Wis1-S159A rev</i>	5' CTGATCTTGTTGACTACTTCCGGCA TTCGTTTTGATCTAGATGCATGGAAG GCC ^{3'}	
<i>Wis1-S226A fwd</i>	5' GGAATCCTTTACTCAACCGTCCAA CGGCCTTCAATCGACAAACGAGAAT CCGTCG ^{3'}	Oligos to mutate T226 of <i>wis1</i> gene to Ala (in red).
<i>Wis1-S226A rev</i>	5' CGACGGATTCTCGTTTGTCGATTGA AGGCCGTTGGACGGTTGAGTAAAGG ATTCC ^{3'}	
<i>Wis1-T225A-S226A fwd</i>	5' GGAATCCTTTACTCAACCGTCCAG CGGCCTTCAATCGACAAACGAGAAT CCGTCG ^{3'}	Oligos to mutate T225 and S226 of <i>wis1</i> gene to Ala (in red).
<i>Wis1-T225A-S226A rev</i>	5' CGACGGATTCTCGTTTGTCGATTGA AGGCCGCTGGACGGTTGAGTAAAGG ATTCC ^{3'}	
<i>Wis1-T225E-S226D fwd</i>	5' GGAATCCTTTACTCAACCGTCCAG AGGATTTCAATCGACAAACGAGAAT CCGTCG ^{3'}	Oligos to mutate T225 to Glu and T226 to Asp of <i>wis1</i> gene (in red).
<i>Wis1-T225E-S226D rev</i>	5' CGACGGATTCTCGTTTGTCGATTGA ATCCTCTGGACGGTTGAGTAAAGG ATTCC ^{3'}	

Table S3. Oligonucleotides used

Supplementary Original western blot and kinase assays images

Fig. 1a

Fig. 1b

Fig. 1c

Fig. 1c (replicate)

Fig. 1d

Fig. 2a

Fig. 2b

Fig. 2c

Fig. 3a

Fig. 3b

Fig. 5a

Fig. 5a (phosphorylation of Wis1 and Wis1-4A, replicate)

Fig. 6a

Fig. 6b

Fig. 6c

